

TABLE 1—1-CARBO-2'-PHENYL-1', 2', 3',-TRIAZOLYL-4-ARYL-THIOSEMICARBAZIDES (I)

S. No.	Ar	Yield %	M. P. °C	Mol. Formula	N		Analysis % S	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1	C ₆ H ₅	65	138-9	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ OS	24.85	24.81	9.47	9.42
2	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70	182-3	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ S	22.83	22.75	8.69	8.63
3	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	64	190-1	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₆ OSCl	22.55	22.4	8.59	8.54
4	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	68	182	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ OS	23.86	23.79	9.09	9.01
5	2-Naphthyl	60	117-8	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ OS	21.65	21.59	8.25	8.21

TABLE 2—2-PHENYL-4(4'-PHENYL-5'-MERCAPTO-1', 2', 4'-TRIAZOLYL)-1, 2, 3-TRIAZOLES (II).

S. No.	Ar	M. P. °C	Yield	Mol. Formula	N		Analysis % S	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
6	C ₆ H ₅	223-4	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ S	26.25	26.21	10.00	9.96
7	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	225-6	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₆ OS	24.00	23.92	9.14	9.10
8	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	264-5	56	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₆ SCl	23.70	23.64	9.03	8.98
9	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	196-7	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₆ S	25.16	25.11	9.58	9.55
10	2-Naphthyl	247-8	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ S	22.71	22.68	8.65	8.61

2-Phenyl-4 (4'-aryl substituted-5'-mercapto-1', 2', 4'-triazolyl)-1, 2, 3-triazoles (II) (Table 2): The compound I (0.01 mole) and 2N sodium hydroxide (20 ml) were refluxed for 3 hr. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The desired compound thus precipitated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. All the other bis-triazoles were prepared by this method.

Well powdered plant was extracted with chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol successively. The chloroform extract on chromatography over neutral alumina yielded substances A, B and C in workable yields. Ethyl acetate extract on chromatography over silica gel gave another substance D while chromatography of the brown deposit from methanolic extract over magnesium yielded substance E.

References

1. N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG and N. H. NAM., *C. R. Acad. Sci. (Paris)*, 1954, 238, 295.
2. N. P. BUU-HOI, N. D. XUONG, J. D. BAZARE, Z. SCHEMBRI, N. H. NAM and C. T. LONG., *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 50, 13916.
3. C. RUNTI and F. COLLINS, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 57, 7137.
4. M. WELSCH, N. P. BUU-HOI, P. DANTHINE and N. D. XUONG., *Experimentia*, 1956, 12, 102.
5. T. ZSOLNAI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 52, 6431c.
6. W. E. MAYBERRY, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1968, 129, 551.
7. K. C. JOSHI and J. S. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 32, 320.
8. J. L. REIBSOMER and GENE SUMRELL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 807.
9. F. B. DANIS, R. Q. BREWSTER and C. P. OLANDER, *Org. Synth., Coll. Vol. I*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., N. Y. 1932, p. 437.

Chemical Constituents of *Scutia myrtina* Kurz

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Manuscript received 9 April 1976; accepted 24 May 1976

SCUTIA myrtina Kurz. (Rhamnaceae) was found to possess significant antiprotozoal, antihelminthic and antiviral activity¹. This prompted us to undertake chemical investigation of this species. No chemical studies have so far been reported on this plant.

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Substance A, m.p. 81°-82° was identified as tetratricontane-22-01-13-one (Grewinol)². Substance B, m.p. 136° was characterized as β-sitosterol (m.p., m.m.p., Co-TLC, IR) and substance C, m. p. 98° as tetratriacontanoic acid (IR, mass, identical derivatives). Substance D, m.p. 165°-8° was a flavone glycoside and was identified as quercetin 3.0-β-D-glucoside by various colour reactions, UV, acid hydrolysis and identical m.p. Substance E, m.p. 240° dec. was characterized as leucocyanidin by m.p., various colour reactions, UV spectral data, degradations etc.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Professor T. R. Govindachari, Director, CIBA Research Centre, Bombay for spectra and SCST for financial assistance, to one of us.

References

1. M. L. DHAR, M. M. DHAR, B. N. DHAWAN, B. N. MEHROTRA and C. ROY. *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1968, 6, 232.
2. Structure of Grewinol from the flowers of *Grewia asiatica* Linn. LLOYDIA (In press).